

A Biblical Evaluation of the Function of Religion in the Nigerian 2023 Presidential Election

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Abstract

The place and function of religion in secular leadership and national politics has been witnessed as dramatic in the concluded February 2023 Presidential elections in Nigeria. The elections witnessed an unprecedented sensitivity to the religion of the public office holder or aspirer, in which the religion a candidate subscribes to becomes a determining factor in the eventual choice of the electorates. This is particularly the case with the choice of the presidential flag bearers of the All Progressive Congress (APC) political party and the Labour Party, in contest with that of the PDP. In the electioneering process, deep divisive religious sensitivity was expressed across entire Nigeria. While some notable Nigerians and groups saw the 2023 APC same-faith presidential flag-bearers as bad omen, others saw it as a political and electoral strategy. In spite of all this, the elections went decisively and the Presidential victor imaged, in the person of Asiwaju Bola Ahmed Tinubu, of the APC. The development has serious implication on the place and function of religion in secular politics. This paper, from a biblical perspective, uses a critical approach in interpreting the religious forces and influences that have shaped the development so as to determining their consistencies with biblical truth and well-being of Nigerian politics. The aim of the paper is to point out the fallacy and fables of religious influences on Nigerian politics, politicians and people.

Keywords: Religion, Biblical, Politics, Fallacy, Nigeria

Introduction

A popular observation in the 2023 general elections in Nigeria is that, followers of (some) political parties simply settled for their presidential flag-bearers (and their running mates) on religious ground. Notable and perplexing among these is the Labour Party (LP) which has settled for the presidential candidate in the persons of Mr Peter Obi. This development has generated a lot of tensions reactions across Nigeria. LP followers criticized the APC for citing “electoral value,” “vote counts” and “competence” as some of the key rationale for the same-faith choice, in the persons of Ahmed Tinubu and Kashim Shetima, accusing them of intending a religious suppression of some faith(s). Reactions to these have basically been grouped into three categories: Those against the same-faith choice, those in support, and those neutral to the “new” development in Nigerian electioneering processes –viewing from the ‘83 Buhari/Idiagbon, and ‘93 Abiola/Kingibe unperturbed Presidential same-faith candidacies.

The bases for these reactions may not be far-fetched, looking at the existing ethno-religious experiences in the country. In recent time, ethno-religious conflicts between the North and the South have been messy! Nigeria

is a West African country dividable into virtually two equal religious groups. The southern part is predominantly Christian while the northern part is majorly Muslim. The APC in the southern part freely presented a Muslim as its presidential candidate while the North presented likewise a Muslim as his running mate. This choice unsettles the Christian North, Christian associations and Christians generally across Nigeria. They argue that it is an unjust, imbalance choice which may end up marginalizing and unleashing unfair treatment on the other faith(s) in the running and scheme of things in Nigeria and the world at large. Some Muslims also objected to this same-faith choice, while others see no hullabaloo about it.

Nobel Laureate Professor Wole Soyinka, speaking at the historic Abeokuta Club 50th Anniversary in Ogun State, mused that the uproar over the APC same-faith ticket reflects “how the country has been fractured along religious lines and its citizens made to look different from one another right from childhood.” He asserts that such a dichotomy creates nervousness, anxiety and phobia in children.¹ Corroborating this, Femi Falana, a prominent human right and constitutional lawyer, noted that the agitation for the same-faith ticket is already heating-up the polity. He describes the current fuse over the same-faith ticket as unnecessary, stressing that such fuss never occurred in the Second Republic, especially in Lagos, Ogun and Oyo States, nor during the 1993 nationwide Abiola-Kinghbe presidential tick.²

The debate and responses continue as to the viability and invalidity of the same-faith choice. In fact, initially the polarizing views generated by the same-faith ticket forced the APC to be reluctant and to postpone the unveiling of Shettima as Tinubu’s running mate, without giving any official reason or any new date either.³ Therefore, this article shall present a biblical evaluation of the way religion has functioned in respect to the same-faith choice, pointing out some of its implications to the ethno-religious perceptions, politics and governance in Nigeria –a critical presentation all aimed at a harmonious, prosperous and progressive Nigeria.

Opposing Views to the Same-faith Presidential Ticket

One of the most outspoken prominent personalities against the same-faith ticket was Babachir Lawal, a former Secretary to the Government of the Federation. To him, Muslim-Muslim Presidential ticket is a “disastrous error.” The choice of Kassim Shetima as the Vice Presidential candidate to Ahmed Bola Tinubu was “cornered by self-serving, hero-worshiping, lapdogs.” He claimed that northern Governors and some northern Muslim elites persuaded him that they would never vote for a ticket of northern Christian; “they will massively vote for one of their sons because it is their nature to do so. Tinubu should not think a Muslim-Muslim ticket will win him the northern Muslim votes, looking at the merits and demerits of both tickets’ permutations. There might be some collateral damages though.”⁴

Prior to this, Babachir did have a consuming passion for Tinubu since 2011 to succeed Buhari. With the twist in the same-faith ticket, he believes sycophants and lapdogs might have lied to Tinubu, taking advantage of his listening ears and presidential ambition. “Abuja equivalent are people inflicted with the modern Nigerian disease –religious bigotry, sycophancy and morbid tribalism.” Muslim-Muslim ticket is a “satanic resort,” argues Babachir Lawal, while seeing Shetima as an “overambitious man who has a Machiavellian bent.” The ticket meant the gods want to destroy APC (All Progressives Congress) political party.⁵

Babachir continues, “Tinubu has chosen to bring religion to the front burner of Nigerian politics.” Christians all over will revolt and bring the chances of APC into serious jeopardy. It will jeopardize the chances of Christians seeking elections in Christian dominated areas. It will make APC a minority party. Considering the following contraptions, Christians will not vote for the APC: 1. Muslim Presidential ticket –Lagos; 2. Muslim Vice Presidential candidate –Borno; 3. National Chairman –Nassarawa; 4. Deputy National Chairman –Borno; 5. Nigerian President –Kastina; 6. Senate President –Yobe; 7. Speaker –Lagos; 8. Deputy Speaker –Plateau, etc.

If Tinubu continues and becomes President, “he will face massive discontent and opposition even before taking off.” It is a grave injustice and discrimination against a large segment of the society. Religious extremism/exclusivism as a tool to power or governance is very dangerous. With the ticket, the Christians foresee an Islamic Republic of Nigeria. There is gloom among the Christian community all over the country since the

ticket was announced. More so, proof of possible Islamic agenda was leaked when Governor Ganduje of Kano State gave an advance notice that Tinubu has assured them of picking a Muslim running-mate. Meanwhile, Ganduje has a foundation of which purpose is to “provide selfless service to humanity and Islam.”⁶ The ticket is a deliberately senseless act of provocation, Babachir argues on. It will set both religions apart and at war, while both want to live together in peaceful coexistence. The President and the APC National chairman should respect this. “The ticket will drag down the whole APC members to the pit. We all should reject it.”⁷

On his part, Rev’d Father Oluoma Chinenye John, a popular priest of the Catholic Archdiocese of Abuja, aka Fada Oluoma, says if Bola Tinubu wins, Muslims will continue in power after his terms. The Muslim-Muslim ticket would continue to trigger religious sentiments in the country. So, aggrieved citizens should vote for a better political party in the coming presidential elections. By this, “we will change the status-quo, making informed decisions.”⁸ The choice of the Muslim-Muslim ticket is not a religious problem; do not lose the big picture, claims Father Oluoma. The only major reason for the choice is electoral victory –significant votes from the North. The choice is “more of political dexterity...APC chose electoral votes over religious sentiments.” Whoever eventually becomes the President, in this scenario in particular, depends on the votes. If APC wins, next President will be Muslim. This means “kindred sentiments like tribe and religion can be thumped,” asserts Oluoma. He enjoins the electorates to take a choice of Labour Party (Peter Obi) that is driving a political revolution.⁹

APC Christian politicians in the 19 northern States warned of dire, “serious and grave” consequences in the pursuit of Muslim-Muslim ticket. They argued that the country’s unity is of utmost importance (“at this moment of national peril”) –a prerequisite for nation building.¹⁰ The ticket will make it difficult to sell the party’s candidates to their constituents. The Chairman of this group of politicians, Professor Doknan D.D. Sheni, and its Secretary General Ishaya G. Bauka, argued that the situation of the country now cannot be compared to what it was in 1993 when MKO Abiola and Babagana Kingibe, both Muslims, came up as presidential and vice presidential candidates of the SDP (Social Democratic Party).

So, Muslim-Muslim ticket portrays insensitivity to Christians in the country. Christians will view APC as an Islamic party. The vice presidential candidate “picked might have a hand in the Chinok girls saga and other terror activities.”¹¹ The ticket has highly aggravated Christians in the North; it would undermine the chances of Christian candidates in APC in the North. It is a dominating leadership and it violates Section 14 sub-Section 13 of the Constitution. If it were Christian/Christian ticket, would Muslims in the North take it? Muslim-Muslim ticket was not possible in 2015, now is not best for it either, submit the APC Christian politicians in the 19 northern States.

A daily editorial commented that, the announcement of the ticket “has triggered a massive furore.” It is not needed now, for President Buhari has undermined Nigeria’s unity in his seven year rule. APC government has fostered great imbalance on the Nigerian federation; it has shown disregard for the principle of Federal Character in Section 14(13) of the 1999 Constitution as amended. Muslims could be seen holding key positions everywhere: The President, Senate President, Speaker, Deputy Speaker, Chief Justice of the Federation, security officers in Police and the Military, etc.¹² An Abuja based lawyer, Osigwe Momoh sues APC and Bola Tinubu under the suit marked FHC/ABJ/CS/1188/2022. He prayed that Tinubu’s name must not be published in the forthcoming elections, that the same-faith ticket violates the Nigerian 1999 Constitution as amended. Chapter II Section 14 Subsections 1 and 3, 15 and 224(a) say that President and Vice President must come from different sections (tribal and religious groups) of the nation. So, the APC ticket is null and void.¹³

Former SGF, Babachir David Lawal, former Speaker HoR, Yakubu Dogara and other northern Christian leaders (including Adamawa Senator Elisha Abbo, and former Sports Minister Solomon Dalung) vowed to resist the same-faith ticket of the APC in the 2023 general elections. Speaking at the July 29, 2022 APC Northern Leaders Summit in Abuja, they argued that such a same faith choice is anti-Christ in agenda; so, they will use their PVC and prayers to resist the party’s plan. More so, the party “hired fake Bishops to further embarrass the Church.” It is a wake-up call for all Nigerian Christians, and they “will resist anyone trying to discriminate against them and their religion.”¹⁴ The party completely eliminated northern Christians from its NWC and NEC. The same-

faith ticket was also a long term political strategy and not a one-off decision. “It is a deliberate and premeditated attempt to introduce and firmly entrench religion into the politics of the country, which could lead to further disharmony.” With this, APC and its candidates have started religious politics. So, the party talking of competence as reason for the choice is “balderdash and diversionary.”¹⁵

Yakubu Dogara argued that the same-faith ticket is a politics of exclusion and oppression. Tinubu made a fatal error with the same-faith ticket, for it posits northern Christians’ votes don’t count –small in number. It is satanic in dividing the Church in Nigeria into North and South. It will fuel inequality and breed division, which is counter-productive for a prosperous nation. The same-faith ticket denies the justice of God and fails in leadership quality in crisis to have the “ability to recognize a departure of events from routine to novel.” The northern Christian leaders submit that, this period in Nigeria is not 1993 routine.¹⁶ Pastor Daniel Omotosho, a Senior Regional Pastor of God’s Chosen Miracle Church, Barnawa, Kaduna State, called on President Muhammadu Buhari to call to order Tinubu to stop disrespecting Christians for the sake of politics. He should stop using “fake pastors” to misrepresent Christians at the unveiling of the vice presidential candidate on July 20th, 2022, for it was aimed at achieving political gain. If Christians did such, using fake *Imams* and *Mallams*, it could have led to setting the country ablaze, Omotosho queried.¹⁷

In another response to the same-faith ticket, Yakubu Dogara asks Christians not to waste their votes on APC presidential ticket. Using Matthew 25:14-30, he says that the Bible enjoins Christians to invest and not waste resources. He stressed that the ticket is “antithetical” to nation building by derailing from the fundamentals of shared identity, values and vision.¹⁸ APC ignored warnings from CAN, Catholic Secretariat, ECWA and others. Prominent Islamic Clerics and Muslim leaders have also spoken against the same-faith ticket. Muslims alone cannot build a nation out of Nigeria. The ticket fails to realize Nigeria has never attained nationhood, and no divided people have ever built any civilization, argued Dogara.¹⁹

The Secretary General of the Northern CAN, Sunday Oibe, reaffirms their opposition to the same-faith ticket. He says Nigeria is multi-religious, multi-ethnic and multi-cultural society which has never being so divided along religious and ethnic lines.²⁰ Besides, 27 APC Youth groups and the National Youth Council of Nigeria (NYCN) via its President, Solomon Adodo, say the Vice Presidential candidate Shettima should be replaced with a youth, Dr Ibrahim Bello Dauda –there must be youth inclusion in governance.²¹ Reverend John Joseph Hayab, CAN Chairman of the 19 Northern States and the FCT declares that the same-faith ticket of the APC is “a Nollywood movie.” He said that it is out-rightly false a claim that Tinubu met with CAN National Chairman and Pastor Adeboye of the RCCG on the issue of same-faith ticket.²² In the same vein, the new CAN Chairman and the General Superintendent of Christ Holy Church International, Bishop Daniel Okoh declares that the same-faith ticket is an insult to Christian sensibility. Christians feel “there is a deliberate plan to remove the Christian faith from the scheme of things and make [them] second-class citizens in [their] own country.”²³

Finally on the opposing view to the same-faith ticket, Afenifere, a pan-Yoruba socio-political organization, in a very discordant tone, through one of its leaders, Pa Ayo Adebajo cautions about electing Tinubu himself. He warns that Tinubu will give continuity to Buhari’s incompetence. He would subject himself to criminal northern influences. He “sold Buhari to over 200 million Nigerians for his own selfish interest for wanting to rule after Buhari. None of them loves Nigeria.” In his remark, he names Peter Obi of the Labour Party as the best candidate for the 2023 presidential elections.²⁴

Views in Support of the Same-faith Presidential Ticket

Former media aid to President Buhari, Bashir Ahmal says “majority of Nigerians will have no issue if Tinubu picks a competent Muslim as his running-mate” –a vice with the capacity to help achieve his plans.²⁵ Same-faith ticket “will definitely help us to reduce or even get rid of the politics that is solely based on religious prejudice in the country. It has helped Kaduna State,” opined Ahmal. In a more definite tone, Ahmed Gumi, a controversial Islamic Cleric says nothing is wrong with the same-faith ticket. It has nothing to do with religion; it is a strategy

to win the election, to gain votes. “It now depends on the aggrieved electorates to vote their professed candidate; to choose from a wide range of choices.”²⁶

Senator Danladi Sankara, Chairman Senate Committee on Information and National Orientation, says there is no cause for alarm over the same-faith ticket of the APC. The two flag-bearers “are competent, cerebral and tested.” The ticket brightens the chances to secure electoral victory, and the duo will add value to the presidency. Shettima will complement Tinubu “to bring about desired progress and development of the nation. Both are very conscious of the requirements of equity and justice in leadership and public administration.”²⁷ An Agriculturist, Otunba Yomi Akingbade says the ticket is in the “best interest” of Nigeria. Bola Ahmed Tinubu has capacity “to transform and reposition Nigeria towards greatness” –reviving refineries and creating employments for youths. He will assemble competent team to proffer workable solutions to the country’s many problems. Yomi then called for religious tolerance and harmonious coexistence among Nigerians.²⁸

Looking at the complexity of the issue of same-faith ticket, APC National stakeholders had earlier “counseled Tinubu against it and urged him to consider a competent Christian from the North. The convener of the group, Engr Aliyu Audu said however, a rethought arisen that the same-faith ticket is in the best interest of the country. The ticket seeks to prioritize capacity, competence and character over religion and ethnicity; to build an effective working society. Audu stressed that Shettima has a track record of bringing development close to the people despite Boko Haram challenges. He argues that our past experience shows that to think and act otherwise have not achieved desired goal of sense of inclusion. The current decision of the same-faith ticket was made after all seriousness, sensitivity and wide consultation.”²⁹

The Vice Presidential candidate of the APC himself, Kashim Shettima, has spoken on the same-faith ticket. He contends that the same-faith choice is based on democratic values. It has “brought me enormous goodwill messages” from Abia to Zamfara, and “from distinguished Christians across the country.” It is a unifying representative; not expression of primordial sentiments. It is based on the party’s forthright assessment of the threats ahead, “so as to guarantee success in the elections” in view of myriad of opponent to be faced in 2023. So, the APC same-faith ticket is a rational outcome of pragmatic permutations to defeat opponents, and “it expresses Christians’ view for us to retain power for a unifying and transformative governance,” claims Shettima.³⁰ On his part, Abdulahi Ganduje, the former Governor of Kano State says the same-faith ticket would not in any way result in neglect of Christians in Nigeria. Ahmed Tinubu never has intention to Islamize Nigeria. So, Babachir Lawal is “speaking falsehood against national unity.”³¹

Neutral Views on the Same-faith Presidential Ticket

Former Minister of Aviation, Femi Fani-Kayode commented on points he shared with high ranking officials of CAN on the issue of the APC same-faith ticket. He posits a support for Tinubu and his Muslim-Muslim ticket if his Vice is not an extremist who will undermine the interest of the Christian community. APC political expediency is the “real politik” now (as in Britain); to win the 2023 election in view of the opposition. It is not “in any way a betrayal of our values or our Christian faith.” Christians will not sit idly to allow anyone or government undermine their faith or people. Over 100 million Christians feel their faith must be protected and they must be represented at the highest level. Those who dismiss their concerns do so at their own peril.³²

He comments further: Christians will support the Vice President who show and display sensitivity to Christian community over the years, and who they believe they can trust. Not all Muslims are bad, and religion and faith should not determine who our candidates ought to be. Given our history, religion “IS” a factor that cannot be ignored; we must allay fears. If it happens that the President and the Vice President are Muslims, then the Senate President, Speaker of the House of Rep, SGF must go to members of other faith. This can allay fears. “Lebane model” factor-in religious consideration in leadership position since 1975-1990 end of civil war, putting Christians and Muslims in [equitable and just] leadership positions.³³

Fani-Kayode continues in relating the points he shared with high-ranking officials of CAN. He states that issue of religion will play a decisive role in the outcome of the election and in the campaign. We must put Nigeria first, and not allow religion or ethnicity divide us. He then preached that,

We know those that see Christians as inferior beings and mortal enemies. Whether Christian or Muslim, if we have a heart filled with light, compassion, kindness, love and the fear of God, we give nothing but goodness and love. But if we have a heart filled with darkness, prejudice, hate, bitterness, evil and contempt and disdain for God, we have nothing to give but evil and hate.³⁴

Pastor William F. Kumuyi, General Superintendent of the Deeper Christian Live Ministry, reverberates that political leaders need to consult and conduct research before concluding on the same-faith ticket. Presidential flag-bearers should look at the heartbeat of Nigeria and the desire of people before making their decisions. Same-faith ticket of any religion “is a difficult and slippery area. They should ask ...what the people want.” If they listen to the people we will be confident they will listen to us when they get there.³⁵ In support of Kumuyi’s opinions, Femi Adesina, Special Adviser on Media and Publicity to the President says Kumuyi is apolitical; others should emulate him. He stayed true to his calling and never took sides politically. “When he talks we can listen, knowing that his message is not tainted with politics, prejudice or any other considerations.”³⁶

Muslim Rights Concern (MURIC) advised Tinubu to consult with the “Noble Dozen” before picking a running-mate for the 2023 presidential elections. The Director of MURIC, Professor Ishaq Akintola stated that, the “Noble Dozen” is the term for the 12 northern Governors who insisted the South should produce the 2023 President. They are the sincere northern Governors “who disabused the minds of Nigerians concerning the myth of Northern hegemony and a nonexistent Caliphate oligarchy. They demonstrated statesmanship, patriotism and nobility of thought by that action.”³⁷

Summary Implications of the Same-faith Ticket and Its Generated Reactions

With the same-faith choice of Tinubu/Shettima, APC “has chosen to bring religion to the front burner of Nigerian politics.”³⁸ Hakeem Baba-Ahmed, the spokesman for Northern Elders Forum (NEF) worries that the APC same-faith ticket will only make Christians to walk away from Tinubu in 2023, while it will make Muslims to vote for Tinubu in 2023. He submitted however that, the ticket will not make any difference to Tinubu’s electoral fortunes. He queried: “Are the faiths of our leaders that important to how they lead?”³⁹ The following is a critical outline of the religious intricacies underlining the same-faith choice:

1. The key players and dominant followers in the politics of Northern Nigeria are Muslims. It appears difficult to think non-Muslim from the North should represent their interests in such critical post.
2. The notion that the faith and practice of a Southern Muslim are not at par with those of the Northern Muslim is practically playing out itself. Muslim from the North sees a Muslim from the South as inferior or second class in Islam. So, to think Tinubu would fully represent the interests of the North (dominantly Muslim) is unthinkable in practice.
3. At least in the current Nigeria, Northern Christian cannot be the presidential or vice presidential candidate from the North, especially in the ruling party.
4. Religion is the first line of thought, and not indigenization, in Northern Nigeria, especially in critical regional or national politics.
5. Regional interests, and not religious equilibrium or national cohesion are uppermost in who occupies critical positions.
6. The Hausas have only Muslims, the Igbos have only Christians, and the Yorubas have both Muslim and Christian for critical first-class positions in Nigeria. It appears absurd for either to do otherwise.
7. Muslims are out to queue up only for candidate of their faith, likewise Christians for the candidate of their faith.
8. Muslims will not accept Christian-Christian, and Christians will not accept Muslim-Muslim in critical first-class positions.

9. If same-faith choice is freely accepted nationwide, it is a vital indicator of the level of trust, tolerance and harmony among Nigerians across all faiths.
10. Trying a same-faith choice is a hallmark of an objective, civilized politics.
11. Competence, trust and dependability are the qualities that can alleviate the crunch of religious politics in Nigeria.
12. Trying a same-faith ticket is a test of the true nature of religious sentiments and bigotry in Nigeria.
13. Rejecting a same-faith ticket may only be covering our wound and not attempting to heal it.
14. Entrenching the idea of a same-faith ticket may end up compounding the negative religious perceptions about ourselves in Nigeria.
15. Experimenting a same-faith ticket is a test-run of the viability of the call for the downplay of religious politics in Nigeria.

Each of the points listed above call for a more critical look at how we view and use religion in our relationship with one another, and in the running of regional and national affairs in a pluralistic (multi-ethnic and multi-religious) society.

A Concise Biblical View on Same-faith Ticket

In the entire written history of both the Old and New Testaments, there are three religions and two governments mentioned: the religions of Idolatry, Judaism, and Christianity; and the governments of Theism/Theocracy and Atheism. The Scriptures condemn any government that is atheistic. It champions as normative only Judaism in the Old Testament, and only Christianity in the New Testament. It however tolerates and acknowledges any government that is “theo-conscious” in all ethnic groups. This is evident in the cases of King Cyrus of Persia and Governor Pilate of Rome. Cyrus tolerated all religious adherents and allowed them to be free in the practice of their faiths. He motivated them towards the discharge of their religious obligations (the books of II Chronicles, Nehemiah, and Ezra). In the same vein, Pilate rejected inhuman, unjust and illegal treatment of any person in respect of his faith or religious claims (The Synoptic Gospels).

It is however difficult to ascertain whether the Scriptures permit only individual of a particular faith to be the sole occupier of (key) leadership position. For, “the earthly city ‘whose life is not based on faith’ aims at a relative peace, justice, and harmony of wills –which requires compromise” (Horton 258). All governments are established by God, and every person who calls upon the name of the Lord everywhere is acceptable to Him. It is also difficult to point out a scenario where consideration for the faith of an occupier of a leadership position has to drift from the conventional practice on certain parameters. Within Judaism, only godly political leaders who worship Yahweh are permitted. “All of Israel’s institutions...exist under the sign of divine oneness and sovereignty.”⁴⁰ Outside the nation of Israel (like in Egypt of Joseph, Babylon of Daniel, and Persia of Esther and Nehemiah) leadership of individuals of different faiths is permitted in a pluralistic setting. Though “Zion stands as the emblem of God’s worldwide dominion...the nations, at their own initiative, decide what to make of that emblem.”⁴¹

During the Christian era of the New Testament, there is an injunction that every person should respect constituted civil leadership irrespective of the faith of the ruler. As Apostle Paul indicates (Rom 13:1-7), “even unbelievers can rule justly and prudently...under the more pagan circumstances of his day.”⁴² While in Islam, as a case in point, “according to Osman bin Bakar...Sharia includes both particular laws governing Muslims and laws that are regarded as universally binding as a result of a common Adamic origin.”⁴³

As the Scriptures progress from the Old to the New Testaments, and to the Latter New Testament, what one observes concerning the faith or religion of the leader is that, leadership is not a sole right of a particular religion. “Sharing substantial convictions of faith and practice does not inevitably entail a particular...political order.”⁴⁴ It appears that it was the factors of context, situation and tradition that determine the choice of a leader or his co-leader in relation to his religion. It was context in the case of Jews in foreign lands (Babylon and Persia); it was situation in the case of the Jews in post-Exilic period (The Empires of Greece and Rome); it was both

situation and tradition in the case of the minority Christians among the dominant Greco-Roman (pagan) rulers (Pauline and Johanne Periods); and it was solely tradition in the case of Jews in their home land before the Exile (The Monarchy).

Applying this biblical principle –the permissive workings of God in leadership– to the matter of leadership and co-leadership in Nigeria (and elsewhere), context, situation and tradition remain viable trio-parameters that should drive leadership choices in egalitarian, civil and modern governance. “Hegel claimed that the history of the ancient, medieval, and modern worlds was ‘a history of the process of the consciousness of freedom.’”⁴⁵ The extent at which Nigeria best uses these trio-parameters determines the strength of her collective experience of value governance.

Conclusion

Context, situation and tradition are the overriding factors that should determine the consensus on what should be the religion of a leader or co-leader in any given scenario. “The common is determined by the ‘common interest’ [which]...marks a new form of sovereignty, a democratic sovereignty.”⁴⁶ The case with the APC 2023 presidential flag-bearers in Nigeria cannot be different. Putting the opposition and the northern electorates in context, in national politics, APC may have reasoned the same-faith choice it presented. Stout observes that “democracy, like any community, is a ‘process of reason-exchange.’”⁴⁷ Interestingly, biblical record is open to this.

Ordinarily, the North should have easily offered a Christian as its APC Vice presidential candidate to complement the Muslim religion of its presidential candidate. But, Nigeria has not attained ‘nationhood or civility’ yet, as some would claim. Majority are more driven by ethno-religious sentiment than objective, civil reasoning. Recent history betrays us on ethno-religious issues, and it will be difficult to make any key national decisions without putting our peculiar plight into critical consideration, at least for the time being.

Of the lead papers presented in this ongoing 44th National Conference of NASR, KadSU 2023, the Professors reasoned patriotically in respect to the Theme and the same-faith rational of the APC, critically pointing out three factors that have engendered such choice. In such vein, may I say here that, Asiwaju Bola Ahmed Tinubu understands the strategic function of religion more than many popular religious leaders in Nigeria. Those pessimistic and fallacious religious leaders and influential figures could be branded as ones who myopically misconstrued Tinubu’s same-faith choice, because it eventually paid off to his victory in the 2023 Presidential election –as calculated. We now came to be perplexed with the reality of the saying that, “things are because we are.”

In frank display of reality, such saying came to psychologically and existentially conditioned the Northern majority in Nigeria to wanting to have their “faith person” in such a critical position in other to feel belong, feel matter, and feel fare-well in the “uncertain” steering of matters in Nigeria. We have learned greatly, we think, of the use of, attitude to, and perception of religious factor in civil and existential matters, irrespective of the person opinionating it –primarily the “influential” religious and notable leaders. We must learn and be more critical and objective in our approach to religious matters on all matters –personal or collective, local or national, politics or existential, social or inter-relational –in a pluralistic setting as ours!⁴⁸

Endnotes

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